

FREIGHT FORWARDER'S AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS THE MULTIMODAL LOGISTIC PARK (MMLP) IN COIMBATORE**Dr. M. Kowsalya,**Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce with International Business,
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Dr.N.G.P Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-48**Ms. A. Dhanushri,**Student, MBA, Department of Business Administration,
PSG College of Technology, Coimbatore-04**ABSTRACT**

The development of Multi Modal Logistics Parks (MMLPs) is a key initiative to enhance logistics efficiency and reduce transportation costs in India. The study aims to examine the level of awareness and perception of freight forwarders towards the implement of Multi Modal Logistics Park in Coimbatore. The research focuses on understanding freight forwarders views regarding infrastructure facilities, cost efficiency, transit time reduction, digital integration and overall business opportunities created by the MMLP. Primary data were collected from freight forwarders operating in Coimbatore using structured questionnaire and appropriate statistical tools were applied for analysis. The findings of the study highlight the extent of awareness, perception benefits and challenges associated with the MMLP. The study provides valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to improve planning, promotion and effective implementation of the Multi Modal Logistics Park in Coimbatore.

Keywords:

Freight Forwarders, Multi Modal Logistic Park, Awareness, Perception, Logistic Cost, Multimodal Transportation and Logistics Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Logistic play a vital role in trade and economic development of the country. The global trade, industrialization and e-commerce had rapidly growing, the need for efficient logistic and integrated transport system is increasing. The logistic cost in India is higher, to reduce logistic cost, improve multimodal transportation and infrastructure, the government of India has proposed multimodal logistic park (MMLPs) across India. Government has approved 35 locations for development of multimodal logistic park all over India. MMLP is a facility that combing various mode of transportation such as road, rail, sea and air for seamless cargo movement, combining warehousing, distribution, digital system and value-added services like customs, storing, packing and assembly. In Tamil Nadu, government has approved 2 locations for MMLP, Chennai and Coimbatore, known for its significant industrial and export hub. The proposed MMLP in Coimbatore at Karavazhi Madhapur Village. Freight forwarder plays a important role in the logistic by providing various services like coordinating transportation, documentation, custom clearance and cargo movement domestical and international. The success of MMLP largely depends on the awareness and perception of freight forwarder. This study focuses on analysing the level of awareness, perception, challenges and scope of freight forwarder towards MMLP in Coimbatore.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To examine the level of awareness among freight forwarder about MMLP in Coimbatore.
- To analysis the barrier and challenges faced by freight forwarder in adopting MMLP in Coimbatore.
- To identify the scope of freight forwarder business in developing MMLP in Coimbatore.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The study focuses on assessing the level of awareness and perception of freight forwarder about the MMLP in Coimbatore.

- It examines the scope of business opportunities and challenges in adopting MMLP by freight forwarders.
- The study also covers freight forwarders operating in and around Coimbatore, considering their business profile, experience and current logistic practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research Type:** Descriptive Research
- **Area Of Study:** Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu
- **Data Collection:** Primary and Secondary Data.
- **Population Size:** 110 (CHAASAAC Organisations)
- **Sample Size:** 50 respondents
- **Sampling Technique:** Simple Random Sampling.
- **Sampling Tools:** Simple Frequency, Ranking Analysis and Factor Analysis

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Patrick Stokkink, Nikolas Geroliminis (2025)** “On the optimal micro-hub locations in a multi-modal last-mile delivery system” Last-mile delivery causes high pollution due to urban congestion. A Mixed Integer Linear Programming model identifies optimal micro-hub locations, capacities, and fleet assignments. A Madrid case study shows reduced costs and environmental impact compared to traditional delivery. This study proposes a multimodal system using trucks, metro and micro-mobility for final deliveries.
2. **Muklisa Samieva (2025)** “The Role of Multi-Modal Transport in Reducing Lead Times Across Central Asia” This article explores how multimodal transport enhances logistics efficiency and reduces lead times in landlocked Central Asian countries. By Integrating rail, road and air-especially through intermodal containers-handling time is minimized, border delays reduced, and costs lowered. The study highlights the role of initiatives like the New Silk Road and emphasizes that strengthened infrastructure and regional collaboration can make Central Asia a key player in global trade.
3. **Yajie Liu et al (2024)** “Research on the path of low-carbon construction of multimodal logistics parks under the background of “carbon peak” and “carbon neutrality”” with countries targeting carbon reduction, China’s ‘dual-carbon’ goals push MMLPs toward low-carbon development. This paper highlights decarbonizing MMLPs to modernize logistics, support regional growth, and promote sustainability, identifying challenges and policy-driven strategies to achieve China’s carbon peak and neutrality targets.
4. **Prof Debasish Rout et al (2024)** “Enhancing Efficiency Through Multi-Modal Logistic and Port Automation: a Case Study on Paradip Port” This case study shows that Paradip port improved efficiency and competitiveness by adopting a multimodal logistic system and port automation. Integration of road, rail, sea and air transport, along with digital and automated system, reduced congestion, delay, costs, and emissions. The study concludes that continued investment in intermodal connectivity. Technology and supportive policies is essential to sustain Paradip port as a major logistic hub.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Designation			
S. No	Variable	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Owner	8	16.0
2	Director	2	4.0
3	Manager	28	56.0
4	Executive	11	22.0
5	Others	1	2.0
	Total	50	100.0
number of shipments (Cargo Volume) handled per month			
S. No	Variable	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 15 shipments	5	10.0
2	15–30 shipments	9	18.0

3	31–45 shipments	17	34.0
4	More than 45 shipments	19	38.0
	Total	50	100.0
Major Client Segmented served			
S. No	Variable	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1	Export	9	18.0
2	Import	5	10.0
3	Both	36	72.0
	Total	50	100.0
Frequency of handling multimodal shipments			
S. No	Variable	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1	Regularly	32	64.0
2	Occasionally	15	30.0
3	Rarely	3	6.0
	Total	50	100.0
know about the Multi-Modal Logistics Park (MMLP)			
S. No	Variable	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1	Government announcement	5	10.0
2	freight forwarder association	9	18.0
3	social media/news	16	32.0
4	Logistics partners	20	40.0
	Total	50	100.0

INTERPRETATION

The analysis indicates that the majority of the respondents are **Managers (56%)**. Most respondents handle **more than 45 shipments per month (38%)**, reflecting high cargo volume operations. A large proportion of respondents serve **both export and import clients (72%)**, highlighting diversified service portfolios. In terms of operational practice, the majority **regularly handle multimodal shipments (64%)**. Regarding awareness of the Multi-Modal Logistics Park (MMLP), **logistics partners (40%)** emerged as the primary source of information among respondents.

RANKING ANALYSIS

TABLE: LEVEL OF AWARENESS ABOUT THE FOLLOWING FACILITIES PLANNED IN COIMBATORE MMLP

Particulars	Mean Rank	Rank
Warehousing	4.10	I
Multi-Modal Transportation	3.66	II
Digital systems and technology integration	3.48	III
specialised storage solutions	3.42	IV
Value-Added Services (customs clearance, packaging, labelling, final assembly and consolidation)	3.26	V

INTERPRETATION

The ranking shows that **warehousing** is considered the most important service. This is followed by **multi-modal transportation**, which plays a key role in the movement of goods. **Digital systems and technology integration** are given moderate importance. **Specialised storage solutions** are considered less important. **Value-added services** such as customs clearance, packaging, labelling, and consolidation are ranked last, indicating lower priority compared to other logistics services.

FACTOR ANALYSIS

TABLE: PERCEPTION TOWARDS MMLP IN COIMBATORE

Rotated Component Matrix ^a	1	2	3	Group Name
MMLP will create new business opportunities for freight forwarders	.778			Cost Efficiency
MMLP will reduce overall transportation costs	.699			
MMLP will support growth of exports and imports in the region.	.673			
Availability of warehousing inside MMLP will support operations	.644			
Use of digital systems in MMLP will improve transparency and tracking		.873		Digital Integration
MMLP will improve the efficiency of freight movement		.744		
MMLP will improve competitiveness of freight forwarders in Coimbatore		.731		
MMLP will strengthen regional supply chains			.569	Freight Performance
MMLP will enhance coordination between different transport modes			.880	
MMLP will help reduce transit time			.641	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.781			
Total Variance Explained	43.098	55.678	66.660	

INTERPRETATION

The factor analysis extracted three key Variables (**Cost efficiency, Digital integration and Freight performance**) that explain freight forwarders' perception towards multimodal logistic park (MMLP) in Coimbatore, which **together explain 66.66% of the total variance**, showing **strong explanatory power**. The **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Value of 0.781** indicates that the **sample is adequate and suitable for factor analysis**.

FINDINGS

- The majority of the respondents are managers (56%) in their respective companies.
- Most firms handle more than 45 cargo shipments per month (38%), indicating high shipment volume.
- A large majority of the firms handle both import and export operations (72%).
- The majority of respondents regularly handle multimodal shipments (64%).
- Most respondents became aware of the Multi-Modal Logistics Park (MMLP) through logistics partners (40%).
- The Rank Analysis, the study found high rank of awareness about warehouse facility available in MMLP and least rank of awareness about value-added services facility available in MMLP.
- The finding reveal that freight forwarders have a positive perception of MMLP, mainly in terms of cost efficiency, freight performance and digital integration.

SUGGESTION

- Since MMLP is still developing, responses are based on expectation, not on actual operational experience, practical exposure.

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- Conduct regular awareness programs, seminars for freight forwarders explaining MMLP facilities, benefits and operational procedures.
- The study focuses only on freight forwarders and excludes transporters, exporters, importers and customs agents who also influence MMLP success.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that freight forwarders in Coimbatore generally hold a positive perception towards the Multimodal Logistic Park (MMLP). While basic awareness exists, there is a clear need for greater clarity and detailed understanding of MMLP operations and benefits. Freight forwarders strongly believe that MMLP will contribute to cost reduction, faster transit, improved infrastructure development and enhanced logistics efficiency. With effective awareness initiatives, infrastructure development and policy support, MMLP has the potential to significantly strengthen the logistics ecosystem in Coimbatore and promote regional trade growth.

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